

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS ON DEGRADATION PRODUCTS
OF BILE ACIDS, SEX HORMONES, ETC. PART II.
A SYNTHESIS OF KETO-DEOXY-
OESTRIC ACID.

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By the extension of the method for the preparation of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclo-octanone, a synthesis of 9-keto-deoxyoetric has been described. It is interesting to note that the above method can be suitably applied for the synthesis of 1:2-di-substituted phenanthrenes.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 423) a method for the synthesis of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one has been described, where the *trans*-form of the above compound has been found to predominate. The locking of the fused carbon rings in the 8-methylhydrindan-1-one portion of the sex hormone molecules is believed to be *trans*. It, therefore, appeared to be of interest to investigate the results of application of a similar method for the synthesis of simple 8-methylhydrindan-1-one. All the synthetical methods (Chuang, Tien and Ma, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 1494; Kon, Linstead and Simons, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 814; Robinson and Walker, *ibid.*, 1937, 60, 1160), so far described by different workers for its preparation, have led to the formation mainly of the *cis*-isomeride (*cf.* Linstead, Millidge and Walpole, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1142; Linstead and Millidge, *ibid.*, 1936, 480). But the fact that *isolithobilianic* acid and *allo-isolithobilianic* acid, which differ only in stereochemical configuration, give rise on thermal decomposition to two different pyro-acids and desoxopyro-acids (Windaus, Hüchel and Reverey, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 91; Windaus, *Annalen*, 1926, 447, 233, 240) and further a recent synthesis of equilenin from a *trans*-dicarboxylic ester by Bachmann, Cole and Wilds (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 974) must be considered as very encouraging.

An examination of the tricarboxylic ester (III), which was prepared by the condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with ethyl γ -acetylbutyrate according to the method of Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327) followed by the addition of hydrocyanic acid to the unsaturated cyano-ester (I) by the method of Hope and Sheldon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2223) and subsequent hydrolysis and esterification of the resulting dicyano-ester (II), made it evident that on cyclisation it could give rise to three different cyclic compounds (IV, R=H; R'=CO₂Et), (V) and (VI),

Actual cyclisation of (III) has now been effected and investigations, which are in progress to determine the manner in which the ring-closure has taken place, will be the subject of a future communication.

Meanwhile it seemed quite obvious that if the C-atom marked (*) in the tricarboxylic ester (III) be substituted then the ring closure can take place in only one way and the product (VII) can be expected to give rise to a compound of the type (VIII) by following similar reactions as employed in the case of 7-methyl-0.3 : 3-bicyclooctane-1-one (*loc. cit.*).

Further if R in (VII) be phenyl or a *p*-methoxyphenyl group then the sodio-salt of the β -ketonic ester (VII) on condensation with ethyl bromo-

acetate or with ethyl β -chloropropionate followed by hydrolysis and esterification should give rise to keto-esters of the types (IV, R = , X=H, OH or OMe; R'=CH₂·CO₂Et or CH₂·CH₂·CO₂Et), which by the application of Cook's method of phenanthrene synthesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 76) should result in the formation of the dicarboxylic acids (IX, R=H, OH or OMe; R'=CO₂H or CH₂·CO₂H).

Robinson has suggested the names oetric acid and homooetric acid for the above two dicarboxylic acids, which were first obtained by Marian and Haslewood (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1932, **51**, 2771; cf. MacCorquodale, Thayer and Doisy, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, **99**, 327) from oestriol and by Bardhan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1848), from *o*-methyloestron respectively. Later both of these were prepared by Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1997) by different methods. A synthesis of isomeric mixture of *o*-methyloetric acid has also been described by Robinson and Walker (*ibid.*, 1938, 183).

In the present communication a synthesis of keto-deoxyoetric acid (XVI) on the above lines, has been described. Considerable progress has also been made in the synthesis of oetric acid and the homo-oetric acid starting with the *p*-methoxyphenyl compound and this will be the subject of the next communication.

Sodio-ethyl phenylcyanoacetate has been condensed with β -chloroethylmethylketone to yield ethyl α -cyano- α -phenyl- γ -acetylbutyrate (X), which is hydrolysed when α -phenyl- γ -acetylbutyric acid (XI) is obtained as a liquid. The ethyl ester of the above acid is condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate as before to yield the unsaturated cyano-ester (XII). On addition of hydrogen cyanide to (XII), the dicyano-ester (XIII) is obtained as an extremely viscous liquid. This is hydrolysed in the crude state to yield α -phenyl- δ -methyl- δ -carboxypimelic acid (XIV), the triethyl ester of which undergoes cyclisation by sodium in benzene solution. The resulting β -ketonic ester (IV, R=Ph; R'=CO₂Et) could not, however, be distilled in vacuum

without decomposition, so that the sodio-salt of the above β -ketonic ester formed by Diekmann's condensation is treated with ethyl bromoacetate in the crude state and in another experiment potassium salt of the same β -ketonic ester, which is somewhat decomposed during distillation, has been condensed with ethyl β -chloropropionate, and in each case the resulting crude product is hydrolysed and subsequently esterified to yield ethyl 1-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexane-2-acetate (IV, R=Ph; R'=CH₂·CO₂Et) and ethyl 1-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexane-2- β -propionate (IV, R=Ph; R'=CH₂·CH₂·CO₂Et) respectively together with some ethyl 3-methyl-6-phenylcyclohexanone-3-carboxylate in the lower boiling fractions. The diester (IV, R=Ph; R'=CH₂·CO₂Et) is treated with zinc wool and ethyl bromoacetate in toluene solution. The analytical data and molecular weight determination of the higher boiling fraction of the resulting product show that it consists mainly of the unsaturated ester (XV). The above compound on treatment with an excess of red phosphorus and hydriodic acid yields a resinous uncrystallisable acidic product, which undergoes cyclisation with elimination of water by means of concentrated sulphuric acid to give the keto-dihapsic acid (XVI) as a thick gum. The above acid, however, gives a semicarbazone, which after crystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol remained somewhat coloured and melted at 165-75°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl- Δ^1 -pentene-1 : 5-dicarboxylate (I).—Ethyl-acetyl butyrate (67 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (46 g.), acetamide (9 g.) and glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) (*cf. Cope, loc. cit.*) were taken in a Claisen's flask and slowly distilled. A little more than 100 c.c. of a distillate was collected in course of 6 hours, the temperature of the distilling vapours being kept between 110 and 115°. The reaction product was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution well washed with water. The ether was removed and the residue fractionated, and the unsaturated cyano-ester (70 g.) collected at 175-78°/7.5 mm. or 155-60°/3 mm. (Found: N, 5.8. $C_{11}H_{19}O_4N$ requires N, 5.53 per cent).

Diethyl 1:2-Dicyano-2-methylpimelate (II).—A solution of potassium cyanide (38 g.) in water (206 c.c.) was slowly added to a solution of the above unsaturated cyano-ester (75 g.) in alcohol (300 c.c.) and water (15 c.c.). The clear mixture was cooled in ice-water and treated with hydrochloric acid (d 1.15, 46.5 c.c.) diluted with water (32 c.c.) and left at the ordinary temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The dicyano-ester, which separated as a thick oil, was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried, the ether removed and the residual oil distilled at 192-93°/4 mm., yield 69 g. (Found: N, 10.2. $C_{11}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Methyl-2-carbethoxypimelate (III).—The dicyono-ester (II) (54 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid (380 c.c.) for 12 hours when a clear solution resulted. The crude tri-carboxylic acid (25 g.) was obtained by repeatedly extracting the above acid solution, saturated with sodium chloride, with ether and after subsequent evaporation of the well-dried ethereal solution it was esterified by refluxing with a mixture of absolute alcohol (250 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 40 c.c.) for 36 hours. Ice-water was added to the cooled solution and the precipitated oil was taken up in ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and then again with water and finally dried. On removal of ether, the residue boiled at 168°/6 mm. or 154-55°/3.5 mm., yield 26 g. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 59.6; H, 8.6 per cent).

Cyclisation of the Tricarboxylic Ester (III).—A mixture of sodium dust (3.8 g.) diethyl 2-methyl-2-carbethoxypimelate (25.3 g.) in benzene (75 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours on the water-bath, when the whole of the sodium went into solution. The reaction mixture, on cooling, was acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and dried. The benzene was removed and the residue distilled at 156°/7 mm. or 140-42°/4 mm. (Found: C, 61.2; H, 7.6. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.94; H, 7.8 per cent).

Condensation of β -Chloroethylmethyl ketone with Sodio-ethylphenyl cyanoacetate.— β -Chloroethylmethyl-ketone was prepared, according to the method described in B. P. No. 282,412 (Scherring-Kahlbaum) from ethylene and acetyl chloride in presence of aluminium chloride. Ethyl phenylcyanoacetate was prepared by condensation of diethyl carbonate with benzyl cyanide (Hessler, *Amer. Chem. J.*, **82**, 120). Ethyl phenylcyanoacetate (99 g.) was slowly added to a suspension of sodium dust (12.2 g.) in dry benzene (300 c.c.) in the cold and the mixture left overnight. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath with β -chloroethylmethyl ketone (60 g.) for 24 hours, at the end of which period the reaction mixture was cooled and treated with water. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, and dried. The benzene was removed and ethyl α -cyano- α -phenyl- γ -acetyl butyrate (X) (115 g.) was collected at 172-75°/5 mm (Found: N, 5.5. $C_{15}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 5.4 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, on crystallisation from ethyl alcohol melted at 154-55°. (Found: N, 17.9. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3N_4$ requires N, 17.7 per cent).

α-Phenyl-γ-acetylbutyric Acid (XI).—The above ketocyano-ester (112 g.) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (380 c.c.) for 20 hours. The keto-acid, which separated as an oil, was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution, the alkaline solution acidified and the liberated oil extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was dried and after removing ether *α-phenyl-γ-acetylbutyric acid* was collected at 195.97°/6 mm., yield 70 g. (Found: C, 69.4; H, 7.2. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 69.9; H, 6.8 per cent).

Ethyl α-Phenyl-γ-acetylbutyrate was obtained by refluxing *α-phenyl-γ-acetylbutyric acid* (65 g.) with absolute alcohol (150 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (a 1.4, 8 c.c.) for 12 hours. The ester was worked up in the usual manner and was collected at 143.45°/4.5 mm., yield 67 g. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 7.7. $C_{14}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, on crystallisation from dilute ethyl alcohol melted at 119.20°. (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{15}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.4 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Cyano-2-methyl-5-phenyl-Δ¹-pentene-1:5-dicarboxylate (XII).—A mixture of ethyl *α-phenyl-γ-acetylbutyrate* (29 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (14 g.), acetamide (5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (55 c.c.) was slowly distilled as described before. On working up the reaction product in the usual manner, the unsaturated cyano-ester distilled at 200.8°/4 mm., yield 31 g. (Found: N, 4.4. $C_{19}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4.26 per cent).

α-Phenyl-δ-methyl-δ-carboxypimelic Acid (XIV).—The unsaturated cyano-ester (XII) (31 g.) in aqueous alcohol (120 c.c., 95%) was treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (13 g.) in water (70 c.c.). The product on cooling was further treated with hydrochloric acid (d 1.15, 16 c.c.) diluted with 11 c.c. of water in the same way as described before. After allowing the whole reaction mixture to stand for ½ hour at the ordinary temperature, it was acidified with 300 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated oil was extracted with ether. On removal of ether the crude residue, consisting of the dicyano-ester, was hydrolysed by refluxing with concentrated hydrochloric acid (300 c.c.) for 50 hours. Even when the mixture was hot, most of the tricarboxylic acid remained as an insoluble viscous gum at the bottom, but on cooling a small quantity of the tricarboxylic acid separated in the solid state from the clear supernatant solution. The latter was separated and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 169.71°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 6.2; Equiv., 98. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 61.2; H, 6.1 per cent. Equiv., 98).

Diethyl α -Phenyl- δ -methyl- δ -carbethoxyfimalate.—The crude gummy acid, which separated in the above experiment from the hot liquid, was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution was dried with freshly ignited sodium sulphate. The residue (18 g.), obtained on evaporation of the ether, was esterified by refluxing with absolute alcohol (200 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (d₁₈:84, 28 c.c.) for 36 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner and the triethyl ester on distillation boiled at 202.4°/5 mm. (Found C, 66.9; H, 7.9. C₂₁H₃₀O₆ requires C, 66.7; H, 7.9 per cent.)

2 : 3-Dicarbethoxy-3-methyl-6-phenylcyclohexanone (IV₃, R=Ph; R'=CO₂Et)—The tricarboxylic ester (19 g.) in dry benzene (100 c.c.) was refluxed with sodium dust (2.3 g.) for 6 hours on the water-bath. The reaction mixture on cooling was worked up in the usual manner, the product distilled as a viscous oil (7 g.) at 195.97°/5 mm. with some decomposition. It gives a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. From the analytical data it has been concluded that the above product consists mainly of the β -ketonic ester contaminated with a small quantity of the keto-ester (IV, R=Ph; R'=H) formed by decomposition during distillation. (Found : C, 69.9, 70.5; H, 7.2, 7.6. C₁₆H₂₂O₃ requires C, 68.7; H, 7.2 per cent. C₁₈H₂₆O₃ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7 per cent.)

3-Methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexanone, Ethyl-1-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexane-2-acetate and Ethyl 1-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexane-2-propionate.—For the condensation of the β -ketonic ester (IV, R=Ph; R'=CO₂Et) with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl β -chloropropionate, experiments were carried out in the following manner. IV (R=Ph; R'=CO₂Et) (55 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (6.7 g.) in dry benzene (150 c.c.) for 8-9 hours on the water-bath, the reaction mixture was cooled and treated with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid, the benzene layer separated, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried and benzene removed, the crude product (35 g.) was then treated with sodium dust (2.4 g.) in benzene suspension and then ethyl bromoacetate (20 g.) was added to it and the whole was refluxed for 24 hours on the water-bath. Water was added to it after cooling and the layer was separated, washed with water, dried and benzene removed. The crude product was hydrolysed by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid (300 c.c.) for 30 hours. The acid mixture was cooled and the acidic products extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and the gummy residue left on evaporation of ether was esterified by refluxing with absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and

sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) for 24 hours, on a boiling water-bath. The ester mixtures were worked up in the usual manner and fractionated under reduced pressure, when 10 g. of 3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexanone, b. p. 182-87°/6 mm., was obtained. (Found : C, 73.5; H, 8.1. $C_{16}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethyl alcohol and melted at 175.5-176.5°. (Found: N, 13.7. $C_{17}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.3 per cent). About 6 g. of ethyl 1-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-phenylcyclohexane-2-acetate, b. p. 180-86°/2.5 m.m., were also obtained. (Found : C, 69.6; H, 7.5. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 69.36; H, 7.5 per cent).

In another experiment 7 g. of the substance, which mainly consisted of (IX, R=Ph; R'=CO₂ Et) contaminated with (IV, R=Ph; R'=H) were treated with finely divided potassium (0.82 g.) suspended in xylene in the cold and left overnight when most of the potassium passed into solution. Ethyl β-chloropropionate (3 g.) was added and the solution refluxed for 24 hours. On working up in the usual manner and proceeding in a similar way with the crude product as before, the keto-ester (IV, R=Ph; R'=H) was obtained as a lower boiling fraction and a small quantity of ethyl 1-keto-3-methyl-carbethoxyphenylcyclohexane-2-β-propionate distilled at 185-190°/1.6 mm. (Found : C, 70.3; H, 7.6. $C_{21}H_{28}O_3$ requires C, 70.0. H, 7.77 per cent).

Reformatsky's Reaction with Keto-ester (IV, R=Ph; R'=CH₂·CO₂ Et). The keto-ester (10.5 g.) was refluxed with zinc wool (4 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (7.6 g.) in dry toluene (20 c.c.) with the addition of a crystal of iodine for 5-6 hours, when the vigorous reaction which ensued at he start, completely subsided. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the toluene layer was separated and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried. Toluene was removed under diminished pressure and the residue fractionated, when about 2.5 g. of a viscous yellow oil were collected at 186-200°/1.8 mm. [Found : C, 68.9; H, 7.5; M.W. (by freezing point method), 410. $C_{24}H_{32}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7 per cent. M.W., 416]

Keto-deoxyoestric Acid (XVI).—The above compound (2 g.) was refluxed with an excess of red phosphorus and hydriodic acid (d 1.7) for a prolonged period. The reaction mixture was diluted and filtered and the filter paper was well washed with ether, which was added to the filtrate. The ethereal layer was separated, washed with water and dried

over sodium sulphate. On removal of ether about 1 g. of an uncrystallisable resinous mass was left as a residue.

The crude product (0.8 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid ($d. 1.84; 4 \text{ c.c.}$) on a boiling water-bath for 10 minutes. The solution was cooled and crushed ice was added to it, when a heavy oil separated which was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer was washed with water, dried and ether removed. An oily residue, which was left behind, was treated with a concentrated aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate and methyl alcohol when a small quantity of the semicarbazone separated as a reddish powder on standing. The product even after crystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol, was somewhat coloured, $m.p. 165-75^\circ$ (Found : N, 10.4. $C_{15}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 11.2 per cent).

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